

Errors in Long-Term Robotic Surgical Training

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Abstract. Robotic surgeries offer many advantages but require surgeons to master complex motor tasks over years. Most motor-control studies focus on simple tasks and span days at most. To help bridge this gap, we followed surgical residents learning complex tasks on a surgical robot over six months. Here, we focus on the task of moving a ring along a curved wire as quickly and accurately as possible. We wrote an image processing algorithm to locate the errors in the task and computed error metrics and task completion time. We found that participants decreased their completion time and number of errors over the six months, however, the percentage of error time in the task remained constant. This long-term study sheds light on the learning process of the surgeons and opens the possibility of further studying their errors with the aim of minimizing them.

Keywords: Errors · Long-Term Learning · Robotic Surgeries.

1 Introduction

Robot-Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgeries (RAMIS) have many benefits, however, require substantial training of robotic surgeons. The knowledge of how to optimize this training is currently limited. A potential source of information is motor learning studies, however, these mainly focus on simple tasks, spanning hours to days [1]. RAMIS surgeons, on the other hand, perform complex tasks that require years to learn. Towards bridging this gap, we conducted a six-month study in which surgical residents performed complex surgical training tasks on the da Vinci Research Kit (dVRK). We aim to study how surgeons learned these complex tasks over this relatively long time span.

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental Protocol

18 surgical residents with no robotic experience from the Soroka Medical Center, Israel visited the lab 18 times – before, during and after a 26 hour shift once a month for six months. In each visit, they used the dVRK to complete three surgical training tasks. All video and kinematic data were recorded. Here, we focus on the ring transfer task, in which the surgeons extracted the rings from the vertical towers and inserted them onto the horizontal towers using each hand in turn (Fig. 1(a)). The surgeons were asked to do so as fast as possible with the minimum amount of errors, defined as collisions between the tower and the ring. They received no feedback about their performance.

2.2 Data Analysis

Due to the speed-accuracy trade-off [2], we examined both the errors and task completion time. We did this using the video data, which were manually segmented, such that the frames in which the surgeon began and ended the insertion or extraction from each tower were logged. The completion time was computed by subtracting the timestamp of the first frame of the tower from the last, and summing the times of the four towers.

To evaluate the errors, we detected collisions between the ring and tower, reflected as tower movements in the videos. We found the start and end of each movement; each was defined as an error. We first detected the towers using a color threshold, and filtered out noises with a size threshold. Additionally, although the instruments moved and could cause tower movements, the task-board did not move. We utilized this and the manual event segmentation to define a region of interest per frame to detect only the relevant tower in each portion of the video. Fig. 1(a) shows the detected vertical right tower.

Next, we computed all movement between each two consecutive frames using optical flow, and summed the velocity magnitudes of the detected tower pixels (the black signal in Fig. 1(b)). We filtered the signal using a moving average filter with a window size of five samples, and computed the derivative; frames with tower movements were characterized by higher frequencies in this signal. Therefore, we computed Short Time Fourier Transforms (Fig. 1(c)) and detected frames with errors as those whose frequency magnitude surpassed a threshold. Lastly, we cleaned the detected tower movement signals by removing single-sample movements, and combining movements less than 10 samples apart. We computed the number of errors and the error percentage, defined as the total error time relative to the total task time.

Fig. 1. Tower Movement Detection Algorithm. (a) The detected vertical right tower is shown in red. (b) The sum of the optical flow magnitude of the tower pixels (black signal), filtered (red) and derivative (blue). The shaded gray areas indicate the frames with errors. (c) Short-Time Fourier Transform of the derivative.

3 Results

Fig. 2(a) shows a decrease in task completion time, both between the three sessions surrounding each shift, and between months. The number of errors (Fig. 2(b)) also showed a general trend of decreasing over time, however without a consistent decrease between the sessions surrounding a single shift. From Fig. 2(c)) we can conclude that the surgeons did not decrease the percentage of time spent colliding with the towers.

Fig. 2. Averaged Time and Error Results of 18 Participants. (a) Task completion time. (b) Number of errors. (c) Error percentage. The abscissa is the shift number. The three shades of green show the results from before (palest green), during (darker green) and after (darkest green) the shift.

4 Discussion

The surgeons decreased their completion time and number of errors, but not the percentage of time they collided with the towers. One explanation can be that they received no feedback on their performance [3]. They therefore may have optimized their time to finish faster, rather than take longer and reduce their errors. Many surgeons initially made smaller and more frequent errors, and as time progressed, made fewer errors that spanned a larger portion of the task. Despite the lack of reduction in error percentage, the decrease in completion time reflects an improvement in the speed-accuracy trade-off, showing that the surgeons improved in learning this complex task over time. Some decrease in completion time generally also occurred between the three meetings surrounding a shift, showing that despite increased fatigue, learning likely still occurred.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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